

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

GEORGIA – GERMANY: SOCIAL-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OF LABOR MIGRATION

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Abstract

Revealing the factors causing international labor migration, bringing it into the legal framework, and evaluating the socio-economic consequences are the areas of interest for many researchers around the world. Attempts to create theories of labor migration to explain the causes and consequences of migration often end up with contradictory conclusions, which are explained by the complex nature of migration processes and the influence of political processes on it.

The paper analyzes the socio-economic consequences of the legalization of migration processes between Georgia and Germany and the prospects for further relations development between the countries.

Keywords: labor migration, legalization of migration processes, economic consequences of migration.

International labor migration is the concomitant process of global economic integration based on mutual benefits. Like capital and commodity flows, it requires an orientation toward maximizing profits and minimizing costs for both the sending and receiving countries. Migration processes are carried out under the multilateral agreements auspices that regulate trade between countries and investments.

Migration processes are one of the most urgent global challenges of our time, which is mainly related to the increase in unemployment. In many cases, this process is illegal and is associated with certain risks: cases of trafficking are revealed, the rights of migrants are violated, the psycho-social situation in the families of immigrants worsens, etc. Legalization of the so-called illegal labor migration is a priority of many countries around the world [1]. Legal labor migration reduces the unemployment rate; Migrants improve their qualifications and gain new experience, which they then use in their country; Migrants' remittances contribute to the improvement of living standards, both in their families and across the country [2]. A sharp increase in the migrants number is often undesirable for European countries [3]. The governments of the receiving country try to prevent the flow of illegal migrants in different ways. However, in fact, as some researchers confirm, the receiving countries sometimes benefit more from illegal migration than they suffer from its negative consequences. In particular, immigrants are exempted from social protection and sent to the secondary labor markets for jobs harmful to health and hard work under the conditions of minimum pay. In these conditions, migration risk assessment and in-depth analysis of the processes acquire special importance. It is likely that changes in the visa regime with the European Union and Georgia's acceptance of the EU candidate status will contribute to the legalization process of migration processes in the future.

Germany is a significant partner country of Georgia in terms of legal employment. Diplomatic

relations between Georgia and Germany date back three decades. It covers all areas of the public sector, economy, and civil society. Germany supports Georgia in the political and economic transformation processes and on the path to joining the European Union. Georgia's geographical location between Europe and Asia, favorable climatic conditions for the development of the agrarian sector, and tourism potential provide many opportunities for the economic relations development between the countries.

In 2013-2016, together with the German International Cooperation Society, the first trial project of temporary labor (circular) migration was implemented, the main goal of which was the safe and organized employment of Georgian migrants, the protection of labor and social rights and ensuring their return to their homeland. The order of the legal base is on the agenda. In 2015, the Law "On Labor Migration" [4] was enacted in Georgia, which regulates the labor emigration issues from Georgia. Also, on November 1, 2015, the rule regulating the employment of foreigners in Georgia came into force. In order to coordinate temporary legal employment issues abroad for Georgian citizens, the Department of Labor Migration was established in 2018, and later, in 2020, the State Employment Promotion Agency was established, one of which functions is temporary legal employment of Georgian citizens abroad. In the same year, on January 17, 2020, an agreement was signed between Georgia and the Federal Republic of Germany on the "Employment of Georgian Workforce for Seasonal Work in the Federal Republic of Germany." The agreement defined the institutions responsible for the Georgian citizens' employment for seasonal work, employment conditions, and procedures. Within the framework of the document, citizens of Georgia were given the opportunity of 3-month legal employment in Germany. Due to the restrictions imposed during the COVID-19 pandemic, the program of employment of Georgians for seasonal work in Germany has been implemented since February 2021. Registration for

Georgian citizens wishing to be employed is carried out on a special electronic platform - workabroad.moh.gov.ge. In 2022 new component appeared in the agreement signed between the countries. In particular, German employers were allowed to communicate directly with Georgian citizens, which made the scheme more flexible and allowed more citizens to be involved in the program. Job seekers travel to and find employment in Germany in a shorter period of time, with relatively fewer procedures. The program does not involve only one-time employment. People involved in it can be employed repeatedly without limit as they wish. The program is still active and is mainly focused on people employed in the agricultural sector, although participation in the program is not limited to people from other fields/professions.

According to the 2022 report of the State Employment Promotion Agency, in 2021-2022, a total of 1,539 citizens of Georgia started working legally in Germany. From January 1, 2023, to May 1, 2023, 216 Georgian citizens were employed in seasonal agricultural work in Germany. Accordingly, remittances from Germany are also increasing. In 2022, compared to the previous year, the amount of remittances from Germany increased by 51 million dollars (by 33.5%). In December 2023, the amount of remittances from Germany amounted to 21.57 million US dollars, which is 7% of the total volume; The annual growth rate is 27.21%. And in January 2024 - 16.2 million US dollars were transferred, which helped to reduce the poverty level.[5]

Money Transfers from Germany

Source: National Bank of Georgia

It is noteworthy that according to the information of the National Bank, the inflow of remittances to Georgia has been steadily increasing in recent years. In 2022, remittances from abroad increased by 86.1 percent and amounted to 4.4 billion dollars, which is an average of 1,185 US dollars per inhabitant of Georgia. With this indicator, Georgia ranks 8th in the world. As of 2023, remittances have increased significantly from the EU (+25.2%, 32.5% of the total), the USA (+39.6%, 11.1% of the total) and Kazakhstan (+32.4%, 4.8% of the total). Compared to the previous year's figures, remittances from Russia decreased by 17%, although it still ranks first in total remittances with 1.5 billion dollars. In 2023, 1.2 billion was transferred from the European Union, 410 million dollars from the USA, and 194 million dollars from Israel. [5]

In the legalization of migration processes, the 2021-2030 Georgian Migration Strategy [6] plays a significant role, the main goal of which is to expand and refine the possibilities of development-oriented legal migration. The long-term vision of the strategy is based on reducing the negative consequences of migration, in particular, the outflow of highly qualified citizens (the so-called intelligence), reduction of working age and reproductive age population, etc.

Conclusion. Georgia is actively implementing reforms in the migration, security, and justice areas. Government policy pays special attention to improving

the management of labor migration; Promotion and development of temporary legal employment abroad (circular labor migration); Raising the awareness of the population regarding the possibilities of legal migration is actively underway; Georgia's visa and residence policy is being refined; Visa-free travel opportunities for Georgian citizens are increasing; Improvement of professional abilities and skills of employees working on legal migration issues is being carried out.

On December 14, 2023, Georgia received the status of a candidate for the European Union, which provides a new opportunity for rapprochement with European countries, perfecting relations, including the legalization of migration processes, and further strengthening the expectations of sustainable development of the Georgian economy.

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